

An EU-PolarNet 2
Policy Briefing

Strengthening international collaboration for observing polar regions

Introduction

The polar regions are experiencing the fastest environmental changes on the planet due to climate change. These changes do not only concern polar ecosystems and inhabitants, but also constitute a major threat for the global climate and societies. The impact of these changes on the world's system is not fully understood yet.

To understand the role of the polar regions in the changing global climate, this policy brief emphasises the urgent need for better collaboration and inclusion in polar observations and research. It is based on the EU-PolarNet 2 "White Paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system", which offers 80 practical recommendations for EU, national and international policymakers. These recommendations focus on strengthening cooperation between the EU and other countries and ensuring Indigenous Peoples and local communities play a central role in polar scientific projects.

This approach will help support informed decisions to address global climate change and promote sustainable development in the polar regions.

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Photo: R. Badhe

Photo: Ronald JW Visser

Key Issues and Challenges

Climate Change and Environmental Degradation

The polar regions are warming faster than ever, affecting global climate patterns. Melting land-ice and glaciers are causing sea levels to rise and accelerate extreme weather worldwide. Climate change in polar regions also compromises wildlife, makes weather more unpredictable, causes more wildfires and thaws permafrost. Urgent action, both short and long term, is needed to monitor these changes and implement strategies to reduce their impact.

Preserving Polar Life and Societies

Polar biodiversity is under significant threat from climate change, pollution, and human activities. Indigenous Peoples and local communities, who depend on traditional practices like hunting and fishing for their cultural and economic survival, are especially affected. Climate change threatens their way of life, making it crucial to involve them in decision-making processes. Working with these communities ensures that policies are fair, effective, and respectful of their rights and knowledge. Protecting the polar regions is essential not just for local ecosystems but for the health of the planet as a whole.

Existing Initiatives

Current efforts to observe and monitor the polar regions are diverse but remain fragmented, with various national and international programs operating independently. This fragmentation results in several opportunities to close gaps in observation strategies, such as:

- Increase spatial and temporal coverage.
- Improve the standardisation of methodologies.
- Encourage sharing of data and integration.

Methodology

The recommendations in the White Paper were developed through meetings, workshops, and interviews with polar experts in research, data, funding, policy, and Indigenous communities. This input was translated into actionable recommendations for decision-makers, funding agencies, academia, NGOs, and others involved in polar observation. Indigenous Peoples' perspectives were integrated through their involvement in these discussions.

Photo: M. Meredith

Main Pillars and Recommendations

1 Users, stakeholders & rights holders

- Ensure early, funded participation of stakeholders and rights holders in decision-making via existing organisations (e.g., the Arctic Council).
- Foster equitable partnerships with Indigenous communities, involve the business sector, and collaborate with local and global institutions for monitoring.

2 Data

- Enhance use of standards and collaboration among data management bodies, and secure funding for training in data management.
- Align existing polar data policies and promote the principles of making data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).
- Establish overviews on polar observing assets to improve cost efficiency.

3 Polar observing infrastructures

- Enhance integration of in-situ and remote Earth observations, expand satellite capabilities, and collaborate with ESA for polar monitoring.
- Improve technological advancement of observing infrastructures with a focus on sustainability, real-time measurements, and international collaboration.
- Maintain existing infrastructures, establish new sites, and create international agreements for shared infrastructure use.

Photo: K. Latola

4 Funding and societal benefits

- Implement funding mechanisms that empower Indigenous Peoples, local communities, and stakeholders in polar research while facilitating international scientific mobility.
- Leverage climate change impacts and global initiatives to attract funding, emphasising societal benefit in communication.
- Prioritise sustainable national and EU funding, create a funding action group, and advocate for transnational agreements and private sector support for polar observation.

5 Organisational structure and governance

- Establish a polycentric organisational structure based on existing initiatives.
- Include governmental and funding agencies from various countries, each with a relevant national mandate.
- Explore Europe-wide models for coordinated and sustained research infrastructure funding.

6 International collaboration & research

- Participate in polar community events and increase funding for Indigenous Peoples and Early Career Researchers to attend these events.
- Foster collaboration between Arctic and Antarctic groups (where relevant), coordinate observations across regions, and promote transnational mobility through agreements and insights from existing projects.

7 Societal relevance

- Strengthen connections between public and private sectors, research, education, and decision-makers to develop societal services from observations.
- Engage in high-level forums and the planning for the International Polar Year 2032-2033.
- Promote accessible platforms for real-time polar information, develop citizen science communication programs, and highlight the social benefits of climate change monitoring.

Recommendations to enhance the Role of the EU in Polar Observation and Research

- Establish EU-funded calls for polar and climate-related projects.
- Establish agreements among national funding agencies and EU institutions for transnational scientific mobility and a unified polar investment programme.
- Strengthen relations with Indigenous Peoples for example by improving access to polar funding and collaborate on tourism management for environmental protection.
- Develop a comprehensive EU polar policy, led by an EU Polar Special Envoy and enhance transparency in public investments in polar regions.
- Shape EU polar policies with support from existing initiatives like the EU Arctic Forum and Indigenous Peoples' Dialogue.
- Raise awareness of climate change impacts in non-polar Member States, ask support from local and Indigenous Peoples for communication.
- Invest in large-scale international polar infrastructures leveraging international climate assessments and events like the International Polar Year 2032-2033.
- Create a sustainable EU presence at both poles through scientific programs hosted by Member State stations and EU-managed facilities.
- Enhance collaboration with non-EU countries having connections with the poles and engage with China on environmental protection initiatives.

Photo: R. Bahde

EU-PolarNet

White Paper

with 80+
recommendations
to strengthen
international polar
observations

Detailed recommendations with examples are available in the EU-PolarNet 2 White Paper, alongside a mapping of Arctic and Antarctic initiatives.

The complete White Paper is accessible here: zenodo.org/records/10929817

Conclusion

This policy brief gives an insight of the key recommendations from the EU-PolarNet 2 White Paper into actionable steps to enhance international polar observations. By leveraging shared interests between the polar regions, the aim is to establish co-ordination for continuous, inclusive, and sustainable transnational polar observation and research, ensuring high societal relevance and supporting informed decision-making.

To effectively implement these recommendations, the following actions are crucial:

- Forge partnerships with Indigenous organisations, research institutions, and international bodies to enhance collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- Secure continuous funding for long-term research and observation initiatives.
- Establish robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks to assess policy impacts and adapt strategies as needed.

Given the increasing urgency of the climate crisis in the polar regions and beyond, there is an inspiring prospect for policy-makers worldwide to join forces and drive meaningful change. The recommendations outlined in the White Paper and summarised in this policy brief can foster international collaboration and connections with local communities, paving the way for hopeful and positive transformations. The time to act is now, with collaboration levels to be progressively adjusted across different areas and topics.

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